

*Code LiveCode Live, or livecode embodied*

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The concept of this livecoding performance is to only use the sound of the typing on the keyboard of the laptop as the source material for the audio in the performance. Furthermore, the sensing devices embedded in the laptop (e.g. accelerometers, touchpad, trackpoint, camera, the keyboard) are made accessible and mapped (through livecoding) to the manipulation of the sound material. Also the processes of the code itself (e.g. their memory and cpu usage) are used as sensors and used in the performance. As such the performance of livecoding is influenced through its own side effects, transforming the code not only in the common logical, grammatical manner, but as an embodied interface of the machine on our lap.